

Reaction to BB race of F₁^a and F₂ populations from crosses of TN1 and IR22 with 35 cultivars from Madhya Pradesh, India.

Variety	Accession no.	Reaction ^a			
		F ₂ of crosses with TN1			F ₂ of crosses with IR22 ^b
		R (no.)	S (no.)	X ² :1	
					R (no.)
Badshahbhog	B2486	410	123	0.95	614
Bhatagunda	B2835	811	252	0.88	614
Bhatapyagi	B2352	655	229	0.33	806
Kalchi	K2096	376	144	1.87	720
Kanthbhulau	K2579	403	140	0.13	640
Kondi	K1655	370	164	2.33	580
Munagi	M1172	522	180	0.12	464
No. 19	N658	436	140	0.11	324
Agyasal	A330	459	170	1.27	464
Agyad	A544	580	211	1.09	684
Anj ania	A88-2	266	98	0.61	464
Aodiayasela	A509	333	128	1.73	600
Baidahuda	B2221	625	242	3.76	624
Baigan	B970	319	103	0.05	640
Bhonduparewa	B1141-1	274	94	0.03	570
Bhubhusi	B1617	576	179	0.60	544
Cross 116	C615	292	92	0.17	392
Dhaniyaphool	D514	598	205	0.09	605
Dhoulimatia	D800	898	264	3.10	680
Dubraj	D61-11	471	146	0.51	980
Dudga	D116-1	282	113	2.55	836
Dudhsar	D350	658	233	0.56	960
Gang prasad	G760	630	231	1.44	678
Garang	G705	432	143	0.00	640
Gonda	G600	684	206	1.53	706
Hansraj	H175	598	195	0.05	456
Jhili	J273	587	221	2.25	504
Kalmigurmatia	K589	301	87	1.24	488
Karigurmatia	K1191	332	128	1.81	480
Karrigurmatia	K1393	358	144	3.44	520
Lalianjan	L1206	328	120	0.63	520
Laligurmatia	L1267	433	142	0.01	756
Sarpin	S1436	597	226	2.52	720
Aagyasal	A456	599	220	1.41	480
Aagyasar	A518	619	186	1.44	800

^a R = resistant, S = susceptible. All F₁s of crosses with TN1 were R. ^b None segregated for susceptibility.

the 1984 wet season. Only 55 were resistant to race 1, only 1 was resistant to race 2. We analyzed 35 varieties resistant to race 1 genetically.

The 35 were crossed with TN1, which is susceptible to all Philippine races of BB. The F₁ and F₂ progenies were inoculated with race 1. All F₁ progenies were resistant; the F₂ populations segregated in the ratio 3 resistant: 1 susceptible (see table). This shows that resistance in those varieties is governed by single dominant genes.

The patterns of reaction to four Philippine races (R, S, S, MR) are similar to the reactions of IR22, which has the *Xa-4* gene for resistance. Therefore, we crossed the 35 varieties with IR22 and inoculated the F₁ and F₂ progenies with race 1. All F₁ progenies were resistant, as expected, and F₂ populations did not segregate for susceptibility (see table). These results show that the 35 varieties have the *Xa-4* gene for resistance. □

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Classification of leaf blast (B1) lesions

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Different types of B1 lesions are produced on rice leaves, depending on the combination of rice genotype and isolate of *Pyricularia oryzae*, plant age, and environmental conditions (see figure). Lesions are differentiated by shape, size, color, and absence or presence of sporulation.

The lesion type can be used as an indicator of the presence of compatible

isolates of the B1 pathogen or as a parameter to determine host and pathogen interaction. Although lesion type is recorded in conventional B1 nursery evaluations, the range is too narrow to illustrate all variations.

We developed a modified coding system to take into account the major lesion types (see table). Lesion type 1 indicates incompatible reactions of the host to a virulent isolate.

Lesion type 3 is often considered an incompatible reaction controlled by major genes, although the nature of the reaction is not well understood. Many japonica cultivars inoculated with indica

isolates produce type 3 lesions with yellow halo (see figure). Leaf B1 seldom increases when type 3 lesions predominate at the seedling stage. Quantitative evaluation based on type 3 lesions frequently fails to predict disease progress by other compatible isolates.

Lesion types 5, 7, and 9 are considered typical susceptible lesions produced by compatible isolates. Type 5 lesions are common on traditional upland rice cultivars. Disease progress, in general, is slower on cultivars with type 5 lesions than on cultivars with type 7 or 9 lesions. When disease pressure is high, lesions become bigger and many

Variation of leaf blast lesion, IRRI, 1988. See table for the description of each lesion type. The bar indicates 1 cm.

coalesce to cause considerable leaf damage.

Type 9 lesions are frequently observed on highly susceptible varieties at the early seedling stage; plants with this lesion type either die quickly or become

severely stunted. In the field, disease progress on cultivars with lesion types 5, 7, or 9 vary greatly, depending on the level of quantitative resistance and environmental conditions at different growth stages.

Classification code for leaf BI lesion type. IRRI, 1988.

Code	Description
0	No lesions
1	Small brown specks of pinpoint size or larger brown specks without sporulating center
3	Small, roundish to slightly elongated necrotic sporulating spots, about 1-2 mm in diameter with a distinct brown margin or yellow halo
5	Narrow or slightly elliptical lesions, 1-2 mm in breadth, more than 3 mm long with a brown margin.
7	Broad spindle-shaped lesion with yellow, brown, or purple margin
9	Rapidly coalescing small, whitish, grayish, or bluish lesions without distinct margins

In field assessment of varietal resistance, predominant lesion type and disease severity (i.e., leaf area affected) should be recorded separately, to indicate qualitative as well as quantitative resistance at different growth stages. When an entry has mixed lesion types, the lesion with higher code number should be recorded. □

Insect resistance

Donors for resistance to Andhra Pradesh biotype 4 gall midge (GM)

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An unprecedented shift in the population of GM *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) prevalent in Srikakulam and Vizainagaram districts has occurred since 1986. Almost all varieties—including Phalguna and Surekha—known for their resistance in these districts, were severely damaged. The loss in about 31,000 ha was estimated to be more than \$410 million.

We reared the GM population from this area on Phalguna plants under strict quarantine in the greenhouse during 1987, and evaluated 90 GM donors with

resistance to the Hyderabad population (biotype 1) against the Srikakulam population under artificial infestation.

Only 12 donors showed resistance to the new population (see table). All traditional resistance donors, like Eswarakora (resistant to biotypes 1 and 3), Siam 29 and Leuang 152 (resistant to biotypes 1 and 2), were susceptible. In addition, improved varieties Phalguna and Surekha (IR8/Siam 29), Kakatiya (TR8/W1263), Rajendradhan 202 (IR8/W1251), Samridhi (R68-I/Jaya), Asha and Usha (IR22/W12631) were susceptible. All 90 donors maintained their resistance against the Hyderabad population.

GM donors showing resistance to biotype 4 population of Srikakulam in the greenhouse. Andhra Pradesh, India.

CR-MR 1523	T10	Ptb 18
Velluthacheera	T1425	Ptb 21
Vellachenipan	T1432	Aganni
NHTA8	T1477	Banglei

Evidently the Srikakulam population is different from the three known biotypes in the country and is more virulent. Hence, it may be considered biotype 4. Some advanced cultures involving donors like Velluthacheera are being tested for their yield potential and adaptability in Srikakulam. □

Short-duration donors for brown planthopper (BPH) resistance

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We screened 200 traditional cultivars of Madhya Pradesh in Hyderabad in 1987 for resistance to BPH. The standard seedbox screening technique had two replications.